

THE COOPERATIVE LEARNING METHOD OF TEACHING IS AN IMPORTANT TOOL FOR IMPROVING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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Abstract

The article informs about the teaching strategy and methods of training Cooperative learning, which use a variety of learning activities to improve students' speaking skills. The author illustrates that this approach aims to enhance English communication abilities by strengthening grammatical understanding, language proficiency, and self-assurance to convey ideas clearly in everyday contexts. This method's main goals help students become more proficient communicators in English.

***Key Words:** Communicative competence, Cooperative learning, group work, group goals, student achievement, promoted social skills*

Introduction

English is used in all countries as a means of international communication. Today, more and more people agree with this statement because it's necessary to learn English with the development of international technologies and science. We use English as a means of communication and for different purposes. English is one of the important subjects in school curricula at colleges, academic lyceums, and higher schools as well.

There have been reforms in the curriculums and programmes of the secondary and higher educational establishments now. The requirement for effective English language teaching is increasing immensely.

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoev, PP-2909, "On measures to further development of the system of higher education," adopted on April 20, 2017, it is stated about close partnership relationships with leading foreign scientific-educational establishments, wide use of modern pedagogical technologies, curriculums, and studying-methodical materials based on international educational standards, creation and wide implementation into the system of higher education textbooks and manuals of the new generation, steady increasing of the level and quality of professional skill of pedagogical staff, and other actual issues.

Every child is an individual, developing at his or her own pace and differing in needs, abilities, interests, cultural influence, learning patterns, and behaviors. Some children are primarily visual learners, whereas others are auditory learners. Some prefer individualistic learning, whereas others learn best in groups.

In addition, different learning styles and strategies are exhibited at different ages, when learning different subjects, or when confronted with different kinds of problems. These differences, therefore, must be taken into account when choosing appropriate teaching methods and activities in the classroom.

There are many methods of teaching languages. Some have fallen into relative obscurity, and others are widely used; still others have a small following but offer useful insights. English is widely spoken in the world. It is the language of art, the humanities, and the social sciences. International trade, commerce, and diplomacy are conducted in English. However, many people around the world fail to enhance their English proficiency, especially speaking skills.

In many countries, English is taught in primary schools traditionally using the grammar translation method, ignoring students' speaking skills. This method was widely used in the past, and even now, many teachers follow this tradition. With

the development of technology, the methods of teaching and learning have also been developed. Nowadays, there are many methods that are being used by the teachers in class.

I would like to write about the process of teaching and cooperative learning in improving students' speaking skills by using methods. The cooperative learning method of teaching is an important tool in the learning process. This method is designed to improve the ability to communicate in English by improving grammatical knowledge, language skills, and confidence to communicate effectively in real-life situations. The main objectives of this method are to develop learners' communication skills in English, improve grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation, and work on the key language skills of speaking, listening, reading, and writing according to the learners own needs.

Methodology

Cooperative learning is a successful teaching strategy in which small teams, each with students of different ability levels, use a variety of learning activities to improve their understanding of a subject. Each member of a team is responsible, not only for learning what is taught but also for helping his or her teammates learn—thus creating an atmosphere of achievement.

Cooperative learning produces greater student achievement than traditional learning methodologies. Slavin found that 63% of the cooperative learning groups analyzed had an increase in achievement. Students who work individually must compete against their peers to gain praise or other forms of rewards and reinforcement. In this type of competition, many individuals attempt to accomplish a goal with only a few winners.

The success of these individuals can mean failure for others. There are more winners in a cooperative team because all members reap from the success of an achievement. Low-achieving students tend to work harder when grouped with higher-achieving students. There is competition among groups in cooperative learning. Some forms of group competition promote cohesiveness among group

members and group spirit. Cooperative learning has social benefits as well as academic ones.

The success of cooperative learning is based on three interrelated factors:

- **Group goals.** Cooperative learning teams work to earn recognition for the improvement of each member of a group.
- **Individual accountability.** Each member of a team is assessed individually. Teammates work together, but the learning gains of individuals form the basis of a team score.
- **Equal opportunities for success.** Individual improvement over prior performance is more important than reaching a pre-established score (90 percent on a test, for example). A student who moves from 60 percent on a test one week to 68 percent (8 percent improvement) the next week contributes just as much to a group as a student who moves from 82 percent to 90 percent (also 8 percent improvement).

One of the essential elements of cooperative learning is the development of social skills. Students learn to take risks and are praise for their contribution. They are able to see points of view other than their own. Such benefits contribute to the overall satisfaction of learning and schooling.

- **Student achievement.** The effects on student achievement are positive and long-lasting, regardless of grade level or subject matter.
- **Student retention.** Students are more likely to stay in school and not drop out because their contributions are solicited, respected, and celebrated.
- **Improved relations.** One of the most positive benefits is that students who cooperate with each other also tend to understand and like each other more. This is particularly true for members of different ethnic groups. Relationships between students with learning disabilities and other students in the class improve dramatically as well.
- **Improved critical thinking skills.** More opportunities for critical thinking skills are provided, and students show a significant improvement in those thinking skills.

- **Oral communication improvement.** Students improve their oral communication skills with members of their peer group.
- **Promoted social skills.** Students' social skills are enhanced.
- **Heightened self-esteem.** When students' work is valued by team members, their individual self-esteem and respect escalate dramatically.

The role of the teacher is very important in cooperative learning. To have effective cooperative learning group teachers must know their students well. Grouping of students can be a difficult process and must be decided with care. Teachers must consider the different learning skills, cultural background, personalities, and even gender when arranging cooperative groups. Much time is devoted to prepare the lesson for cooperative learning.

However, teachers fade in the background and become a coach, facilitator, or sometimes a spectator after the lesson is implemented. Teachers who set up a good cooperative lesson teach children to teach themselves and each other. Students learn from their peers and become less dependent on the teacher for help. One of the goal of cooperative learning is to teach students initiative and self-reliance. Teachers want to see students seek out their peers for assistance rather than them.

With traditional teaching methodologies, students sit in pre-arranged rows. Class size may be as large as 30 students or more. Cooperative learning works best when group size is smaller. The ideal cooperative learning classroom has about 15 to 20 students.

Students are usually grouped in clusters of 3 to 5. The larger the group size the more difficult it is to organize tasks, manage different skills, and reach a consensus. Because the ideal class size is hard to obtain there will be groups with more members than others.

[Formal cooperative learning](#) is structured, facilitated, and monitored by the educator over time and is used to achieve group goals in task work (e.g. completing a unit). Any course material or assignment can be adapted to this type of learning, and groups can vary from 2-6 people with discussions lasting from a few minutes up to an entire period.

Types of formal cooperative learning strategies include:

1. [The jigsaw technique](#)
2. Assignments that involve group [problem solving](#) and decision-making
3. Laboratory or experiment assignments
4. Peer review work (e.g., editing writing assignments).

Having experience and developing skill with this type of learning often facilitates informal and base learning. Jigsaw activities are wonderful because the student assumes the role of the teacher on a given topic and is in charge of teaching the topic to a classmate. The idea is that if students can teach something, they have already learned the material.

[Informal cooperative learning](#) incorporates group learning with passive teaching by drawing attention to material through small groups throughout the lesson or by discussion at the end of a lesson, and typically involves groups of two (e.g. turn-to-your-partner discussions). These groups are often temporary and can change from lesson to lesson (very much unlike formal learning where 2 students may be lab partners throughout the entire semester contributing to one another's knowledge of science).

In group-based cooperative learning, these peer groups gather together over the long term (e.g. over the course of a year, or several years such as in high school or post-secondary studies) to develop and contribute to one another's knowledge mastery on a topic by regularly discussing material, encouraging one another, and supporting the academic and personal success of group members.

[Base group learning](#) (e.g., a long term study group) is effective for learning complex subject matter over the course or semester and establishes caring,

supportive peer relationships, which in turn motivates and strengthens the student's commitment to the group's education while increasing self-esteem and self-worth. Base group approaches also make the students accountable to educating their peer group in the event that a member was absent for a lesson. This is effective both for individual learning, as well as social support.

Result and Discussion

I learned that the use of Cooperative learning method in the English classes for Tourism management faculty students is very effective and considered the most important tool in the development of students' communicative competence and all healthy cooperative relationships have these five basic elements present. This is true of peer tutoring, partner learning, peer mediation, adult work groups, families, and other cooperative relationships. This conceptual "yardstick" should define any cooperative relationship.

Cooperative Learning Games. Educators often neglect the concept of cooperation. When students learn only how to satisfy their own individual learning goals, they fail to recognize the value of helping one another to succeed. In the real world, people cannot afford to ignore the needs of their coworkers and neighbors. Thus, children need encouragement to coordinate their efforts in appropriate ways and for appropriate reasons. Cooperative learning games let children know that the learning process can be fun if it's a shared experience.

Think-Pair-Share Place students in groups of four. Pose a question to students or provide them with a problem to solve. Students spend two minutes answering the question or thinking about how to solve the problem on their own. After the two minutes are up, students pair up with another group member and discuss the question or problem for another two minutes. Finally, two pairs come together to

form a group of four to share their answers to the question or problem and come up with an answer to share with the class.

Literature Circles. Place students in groups of four and assign them an article, a short story or a passage from a novel or textbook to read together. After students have read the text, have one student draw a picture related to the reading, another write five discussion questions, a third student write a summary of the reading and the fourth student make five connections between the text and real-life or other texts. Students should then share their responses to each individual activity with the other group members. Providing a group with multiple activities allows students to interact with a book in multiple ways and analyze more elements of a text in a shorter period of time than if all activities were completed individually.

From the beginning of our research we have known that cooperative learning method of teaching English is designed to improve the ability to communicate in English by improving grammatical knowledge, language skills and confidence to communicate effectively in real life situations. The methods are highly interactive, with intensive use of jigsaw, role-playing, case studies, group discussion.

In formation of interest to a subject the huge role is played by the person of the teacher. Therefore a pledge of successful mastering a foreign language by the pupil's professionalism of the teacher which should in the work not only take into account the methodical principles underlying teaching, but also to be in constant search of new methods and means of teaching which will recover a lesson, will make it fascinating.

The most useful for this purpose are the following methods: methods of cooperative learning method group works, games jigsaw.

Conclusion

Our experience showed that cooperative learning is a progressive style of group education that has many advantages. For example, while learning a concept, students participating in cooperative learning also learn to work with others in a group setting. Cooperative learning has many advantages, one of its biggest disadvantages is that grouping students together will almost always form a group in which some students are faster learners or workers than others. The students who need more time to understand the work may feel frustrated at being left behind. Alternately, students who learn faster may feel delayed or held back by having to wait for the ones that learn more slowly. We suggest that cooperative learning is good for all students and that it is part of comprehensive school reform efforts.

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